

BALI JOURNAL OF HOSPITALITY, TOURISM AND CULTURE RESEARCH

Journal Homepage: www.baliacademicpublishing.com

Potential of the Hotel and Resort Accommodation Industry in East Lombok District, West Nusa Tenggara Province

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ABSTRACT

Tourism is an industrial sector that increases foreign exchange and the country's economy. Indonesia has natural potential which is the main reference in the tourism sector in Indonesia. Apart from natural potential, Indonesia also has beautiful islands, and has various ethnic and cultural characteristics, so it is able to attract tourists, both local and foreign. One of the islands that is the main destination for domestic and foreign tourists is Lombok Island. Lombok Island is rich in natural tourism that is still natural and cultural values that still maintain their authenticity. Lombok Island is an island in West Nusa Tenggara Province, Indonesia. Overall, Lombok has great potential to become a leading destination in the accommodation sector in Indonesia, with a focus on developing quality and sustainable hotels and resorts. This writing method uses literature review and uses qualitative research. This writing aims to (1) determine the potential of the hotel and resort accommodation industry in East Lombok, (2) determine the readiness of the city of East Lombok for the hotel and resort accommodation industry.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Sent 16 October 2024

Accepted 18 October 2024

Approved 11 November 2024

Published 01 December 2024

KEYWORDS

Tourism; Hotels and Resorts;
Accommodation Industry
Potential

1. Introduction

Tourism is a sector that plays an important role in increasing revenue. Indonesia is a country that has natural beauty and cultural diversity, so it is necessary to increase the tourism sector. (Askardiya, 2023) The tourism and hospitality industry is one of the industries that experienced a serious operational, commercial, and financial crisis as a result of the spread of COVID-19 worldwide. At the start of the pandemic, key market players in all areas of the tourism value chain, i.e., airlines, tour operators and hotel.

The Hospitality sector is one of the mainstay sectors based on the economy strived to survive and can maintain its contribution to the economy efforts to reduce open unemployment through increased economic growth is still unable to reduce unemployment. Indonesia has many tourist destinations where this is an opportunity to open this hotel and resort industry. There are many hotel and *resort* industries in Indonesia, reported on indonesia.travel including: *Bintan Lagoon Resort* (Riau Islands), *Padma Hotel* (Bandung), *Royal Safari Resort Garde* (Bogor), *Bvlgari Resort* (Bali), *The Kayana Beach* (Lombok), and many more potential hotels and *resorts* in Indonesia, which of course have varying stars. Therefore, a lot of stakeholders or the government must participate in helping the hotel and resort sector continue to grow and develop. the greater the potential. With tourism in Indonesia, of course, hotels in Indonesia will also certainly get income from tourists who stay at hotels or *resorts* when they travel in Indonesia.

One of the islands with potential in the hotel and *resort* industry is East Lombok, which is part of West Nusa Tenggara Province, has shown great potential as a growing tourism destination. Along with the

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growth of tourism in Lombok, especially after the development of the Mandalika destination as one of the Special Economic Zones (SEZ), the demand for quality accommodation such as hotels and *resorts* continues to increase. The accommodation industry not only provides facilities for tourists, but also plays an important role in supporting local economic growth, creating jobs, and improving the lives of local communities.

According to Budi Supriyanto, a tourism expert Indonesia, *"The development of tourism infrastructure and facilities, such as hotels and resorts, is a key factor in maximising a region's potential as a tourist destination. Without adequate accommodation, it is difficult for a region to attract tourists and compete with other global destinations."* This statement shows the importance of investment in the accommodation sector in increasing the tourist attractiveness of a region.

2. Discussion

2.1. Accommodation Industry In Indonesia

According to the book Hotel and Other Accommodation Statistics in Indonesia 2023, it was written that the condition of hospitality and tourism in Indonesia after the Covid-19 pandemic experienced growth. There are 6 provinces that are starting to rise with the downturn in tourism, namely Bali, West Nusa Tenggara, East Nusa Tenggara, Yogyakarta Special Region, North Maluku, Bengkulu and Lampung.

Based on the results of the annual hotel survey (VHTL), it was noted that the number of hotels in the period 2020-2023 was quite fluctuating. Changes in the number of hotels were strongly influenced by the Covid 19 pandemic which occurred in early 2020 to 2022. In 2021, when the pandemic had a wide impact, including restrictions on population mobility, many hotels were affected. This phenomenon was captured by the VHTL data which recorded a large decrease in the number of hotels (- 10.43%).

Figure 1. Number of Hotels and Other Accommodation Services, 2019-2023

In 2022, when the pandemic had begun to subside, the number of accommodation services businesses grew again and increased considerably (4.32 per cent). Furthermore, amidst the recovery of economic conditions in 2023, the number of accommodation services increased slightly compared to 2022. This data shows that the economic recovery is in line with tourism services. It is expected that this condition will continue in the future

Indonesia, as an archipelago with more than 17,000 islands and a rich diversity of culture, nature, and tourist destinations, has great potential in the accommodation industry. Here are some of the main potentials of the accommodation industry in Indonesia:

A. Tourism Growth

Indonesia is known as one of the world's favourite tourist destinations, especially for destinations such as Bali, Lombok, Labuan Bajo, and Yogyakarta. With the increase in foreign tourist arrivals, especially from Asia and Europe, as well as the growing trend of domestic tourism, the need for accommodation continues to rise. In addition, tourism promotion by the government through *branding* such as *"Wonderful Indonesia"* has successfully attracted the attention of foreign tourists.

- B. Diversification of Accommodation Types Accommodation in Indonesia is no longer limited to large hotels, but is also expanding towards alternative accommodation such as:
1. *Homestay*: Supporting local tourism and giving travellers a more authentic experience.
 2. *Villas and Resorts*: Popular in tourist spots like Bali and Lombok, especially for travellers seeking privacy and luxury.
 3. Cheap *Hostels* and Lodges: Suitable for budgettravellers, including *backpackers*.

Figure 2. Number of Businesses in Star Hotels Other Accommodation by Province, 2019-2023

Provinsi / Province	Tahun				
	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
01. Aceh	451	481	506	548	549
02. Sumatera Utara	1.191	1.452	1.412	1.352	1.353
03. Sumatera Barat	708	809	842	869	946
04. Riau	503	506	477	525	528
05. Jambi	225	235	236	216	217
06. Sumatera Selatan	447	478	487	567	568
07. Bengkulu	186	233	222	246	248
08. Lampung	310	411	363	438	439
09. Kep. Bangka Belitung	176	196	183	198	200
10. Kepulauan Riau	453	463	397	394	398
11. DKI Jakarta	991	939	893	878	870
12. Jawa Barat	3.191	3.145	3.088	3.103	3.119
13. Jawa Tengah	2.036	2.006	2.003	1.986	2.019
14. D.I. Yogyakarta	1.817	1.848	1.696	1.818	1.820
15. Jawa Timur	4.132	4.293	3.815	3.782	3.783
16. Banten	490	534	453	458	458
17. Bali	4.419	4.784	3.345	3.874	3.895
18. Nusa Tenggara Barat	1.055	1.068	603	888	892
19. Nusa Tenggara Timur	529	525	487	605	612
20. Kalimantan Barat	493	524	508	502	509
21. Kalimantan Tengah	490	518	495	509	514
22. Kalimantan Selatan	406	478	440	491	491
23. Kalimantan Timur	706	670	650	628	629
24. Kalimantan Utara	140	143	143	138	138
25. Sulawesi Utara	310	339	290	266	266
26. Sulawesi Tengah	599	668	661	611	613
27. Sulawesi Selatan	951	1.033	1.000	986	993
28. Sulawesi Tenggara	470	527	483	466	467
29. Gorontalo	113	127	125	134	135
30. Sulawesi Barat	152	172	143	163	163
31. Maluku	343	362	368	355	356
32. Maluku Utara	267	278	289	317	318
33. Papua Barat	228	238	235	228	229
34. Papua	265	260	277	269	270
Indonesia	29.243	30.823	27.607	28.800	29.005

Catatan: Angka pada tahun 2022 adalah angka revisi

Overall, Indonesia saw a steady increase in the number of accommodations from 2019 (29,243 accommodation) to 2023 (29,005 accommodations). Although there was a slight decline in 2021 due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the sector showed signs of recovery in the following years.

Several other provinces also showed consistent improvement, such as West Nusa Tenggara (NTB), which saw an increase from 1,055 accommodations in 2019 to 1,115 in 2023, as well as the growing provinces of North Sumatra and West Sumatra.

Provinces that rely on the tourism sector, such as Bali and NTB, show significant growth in accommodation. This increase is directly related to the growing number of domestic and foreign tourist arrivals. Bali remains the main centre, but destinations such as Lombok in NTB and South Sulawesi are also growing in popularity among travellers.

Determination of the type of hotel based on the demands of guests in accordance with the decision of the Indonesian Minister of Transportation No.PM10/PW.301/phb-77, is divided into:

1. *Business hotel*, which is a hotel with the purpose of serving guests who have business interests.
2. *Tourist hotel*, which aims to serve guests who will visit tourist attractions.
3. *Sport hotel*, which is a specialised hotel for guests who aim for sports or sports.
4. *Research hotel*, which is an accommodation facility provided for guests who aim to conduct research.

While the classification of hotels is seen from the location of the hotel according to the Decree of the Director General of Tourism SK: Kep22/U/VI/78, hotels are divided into two, namely:

1. Resort hotels (beach/mountain), which are hotels located in tourist areas, either mountains or beaches. This type of hotel is generally used by tourists who come for tourism or recreation.

2. City hotels, which are hotels located in urban areas, are generally used to conduct business activities such as meetings or company meetings.

C. Advances in Technology and Online Platforms

Accommodation in Indonesia is increasingly integrated with online platforms such as Traveloka, Agoda, and Airbnb, making it easier for travellers to book a stay. These technological advancements also help small-scale accommodation businesses to reach a wider market.

D. Focus on Sustainable Tourism Global trends towards tourism

The rise of sustainability has led many accommodation industry players in Indonesia to start adopting sustainability principles, such as the use of renewable energy and waste reduction. This has created a new market segment, especially for travellers who care about the environment.

Figure 3. Development of Hotels and Other Accommodation Services By Province 2023

In total, the number of accommodation service businesses in Indonesia experienced a slight increase in 2023. When viewed per province the condition is also not much different. In general, the number of accommodation services from 2022-2023 remained or slightly increased. This is in line with the development of priority tourist destinations that are diverse and not only focused on tourism.

2.2. Accommodation Industry Benefits

The accommodation industry boosts the local economy by creating jobs, encouraging consumption of local goods and services, and contributing through taxes. Travellers staying in a hotel or other accommodation will spend money on various necessities during their stay, which in turn strengthens the local economy. Here are some of the key benefits of the accommodation industry:

A. Economic Growth Driver Accommodation industry contributes directly on the economy through:

1. Hotels, resorts, hostels, and other inns create jobs because the hospitality business requires labour in various fields, such as management, guest services, cleaning, and security.
2. Accommodation that attracts tourists increases tax revenue, especially through hotel and restaurant taxes, and increases local revenue.

3. The accommodation industry also supports other sectors other sectors such as transport, restaurants, trade, and tourism services.

B. Infrastructure Development

The growth of the accommodation industry fuelled the development of infrastructure such as roads, airports, and transport facilities. This investment not only benefits the tourism sector but also the local community, with better access to public facilities.

C. Promotion of Local Culture and Tourism Accommodation Industry Supports Promotion of Local and Tourism Through:

1. Lodgings such as homestays or traditional villas allow travellers to experience the local culture first-hand, creating an authentic local experience.
2. The industry often works closely with local residents to provide authentic tourism experiences, which in turn boosts the local economy.

D. Improved Service Quality and HR Competence

The accommodation industry encourages training and development of human resources, especially in the areas of customer service, hotel management, and other specialised skills. This improvement in the quality of human resources strengthens the competitiveness of Indonesian tourism in the global arena.

E. Multiplier Effect

The accommodation industry has a ripple effect on other sectors such as:

1. The growth of supporting businesses such as restaurants, souvenir shops, tour service providers, and local transport will benefit from the presence of a hotel or inn.
2. Many micro and small enterprises develop around the accommodation industry, such as laundry, vehicle rental, or catering for the travelling public. travellers, which is also known as opening up business opportunities.

F. Increasing Investment

The growth of the accommodation industry encourages investment from the private sector, both local and international. This investment is not only limited to the construction of new accommodation but also the improvement of facilities, such as hotel renovations to meet international standards.

2.3. Regional Profile of East Lombok Regency

East Lombok is one of the districts in West Nusa Tenggara (NTB) Province, located in the eastern part of Lombok Island. This region is known to have extraordinary natural beauty, including mountains, exotic beaches, and natural tourist destinations that have not been widely explored.

Geographically, East Lombok Regency is located between 116° - 117° East longitude and between 8° - 9° South latitude, with regional boundaries:

1. West: North Lombok and Central Lombok districts
2. East : Alas Strait
3. North: Java Sea
4. South: Indonesian Ocean

The total area of Lombok Timur Regency is 2,679.88 km², consisting of 1,605.55 km² (59.91%) of land and 2,679.88 km² of water.

The ocean covers an area of 1,074.33 km² (40.09%). The land area of East Lombok Regency covers 33.88% of Lombok Island or 7.97% of the land area of West Nusa Tenggara Province. The plains of East Lombok include mountains and lowlands which stretches to the coast. Mountainous areas are found in

the northern part of the region, namely the Gunung Rinjani National Park area with a peak height of 3,726 metres above sea level.

Figure 4. Population of Lombok Timur Source: Central Bureau of Statistic-Population and Civil Registration Office/ Regional Population and Civil Registry Office Of Lombok Timur Regency

Kecamatan	Jumlah Penduduk	Laju Pertumbuhan Penduduk per Tahun	Persentase Penduduk	Kepadatan Penduduk per km persegi (km ²)	Rasio Jenis Kelamin Penduduk
Pringgabaya	117.161,0	1,00	8,34	860	98,1
Suela	48.513,0	0,83	3,45	422	98,6
Aikmel	74.219,0	0,97	5,28	915	98,2
Wanasaba	74.466,0	1,07	5,30	1.332	98,2
Semabalun	25.190,0	1,10	1,79	116	102,3
Lenek	47.444,0	1,40	3,38	1.134	97,5
Sambelia	40.147,0	0,47	2,86	164	101,1
Lombok Timur	1.404.343,0	0,88	100,00	875	99,2

Based on data on the total population of East Lombok, which reaches around 1.4 million people, East Lombok has a significant population to support various economic sectors, including the tourism, agriculture and fisheries industries. The majority of East Lombok's population comes from the Sasak tribe, an indigenous tribe of Lombok that has a rich culture and strong traditions, which can be a major attraction in the development of the cultural tourism sector.

Overall, Lombok Timur has geographical and demographic variations which favour the development of various types of accommodation, from budget hotels to *luxury resorts*. The region has great potential in the natural tourism sector (beaches, mountains), cultural tourism, and strong local market potential. Sustainable and strategic development is needed to fulfil the needs of infrastructure, accommodation, as well as maintain balance between development and environmental conservation.

2.4. Analysis of Tourism Potential in East Lombok Regency

Tourism in East Lombok is dominated by natural tourism in the form of beaches and mountainous areas, some attractions have also been very famous nationally such as Tangsi (Pink) Beach and climbing Mount Rinjani. In addition to nature, local culture that is rich in Sasak traditions and customs is also a special attraction for domestic and foreign tourists.

Accessibility to East Lombok is getting better with the presence of Lombok International Airport and the development of road infrastructure that continues to grow. This condition opens up investment opportunities for the development of hotels and resorts, especially accommodation with an environmentally friendly concept and supports tourism sustainability. In addition, the potential for renewable energy in East Lombok, such as geothermal energy and solar power, is increasingly attracting attention. With this wealth of natural resources,

Lombok Timur has the potential to become a centre for clean energy development that not only supports local energy needs, but also becomes a model of sustainability that can attract investors and energy industry players. With the right promotion and adequate facilities, East Lombok can become a leading destination that attracts various market segments, from adventure travellers to tourists seeking tranquility.

East Lombok is increasingly popular among domestic and foreign tourists. Tourists who come to East Lombok usually consist of:

1. Adventure travellers who are interested in climbing and trekking.
2. Eco-friendly travellers who are interested in natural beauty and sustainable tourism.
3. Cultural tourists who want to explore Sasak tribal life and local traditions.

Thus, the tourism potential of East Lombok, which includes natural, cultural, marine and adventure tourism, provides a great opportunity for the development of a sustainable tourism industry, as well as a contribution to improving the local economy.

2.5. Analysis of the Potential of the Hotel and Resort Accommodation Industry in East Lombok Regency

Figure 5. Number of Tourist Visits Destinations in Lombok Timur Regency

KODE KEKAMATAN	KECAMATAN	KODE DESA	DESA/KEKURAHAN	NAMA WISATA	JUMLAH PENGUNJUNG		KETERANGAN
					2022	2023	
	JEROWARU	008	EKAS BUANA	PANTAI KURA-KURA	1.120	1.145	
031	MONYONG GADING	007	PESANGGRAHAN	LOTAS KOKOK JOREN	55.927	61.750	
031	MONYONG GADING	007	PESANGGRAHAN	JOSEN ECO PARK	856	25	
031	MONYONG GADING	007	PESANGGRAHAN	JOSEN EVERGREEN	850	839	
031	MONYONG GADING	005	PERJANI	AIR TERJUN TERENG WILIS	1.108	655	
031	MONYONG GADING	005	PERJANI	TELAGA BIRU	188	162	
040	SIKUR	012	JERUK MANIS	JERUK MANIS	1.841	2.379	
040	SIKUR	006	TETEBATU	ULEM-ILEM	2.622	1.456	
040	SIKUR	006	TETEBATU	JALUR PENDAKIAN TETE BATU	951	984	
051	PRINGSASELA	006	JUKIT BARU	AIR TERJUN GUNUNG KURUS	959	281	
051	PRINGSASELA	010	TIMBANUH	PESANGGRAHAN TIMBA NUH	1.830	9.500	
051	PRINGSASELA	010	TIMBANUH	AIR TERJUN MAYUNG POLAK	1.063	1.695	
051	PRINGSASELA	010	TIMBANUH	JALUR WISATA PENDAKIAN TIMBA NUH	322	375	
061	SURALAGA	001	ANJANI	PEMANDIAN DEWI ANJANI "EMBALAN BOROQ"	60.960	76.686	
071	LABUHAN HAJI	005	SUYTA WANGI	PANTAI SURYAWANGI/SEPOLONG	8.500	5.090	
080	PRINGSABAYA	013	LABUHAN LOMBOK	BUKIT KAYANGAN	670	250	
081	SULELA	005	SAPIT	SEBALU	933	863	
091	WANASABA	005	BEBIDAS	WISATA PROPOK	1.130	1.258	
091	WANASABA	005	BEBIDAS	BUKIT MALANG	455	264	
092	SEMBALUN	002	SEMBALUN LAWANG	JALUR PENDAKIAN DANAU SEGARA ANAK	31.774	62.587	
092	SEMBALUN	002	SEMBALUN LAWANG	JALUR SEPEDA SEMBALUN	306	258	
092	SEMBALUN	001	SEMBALUN BUMBUNG	BUKIT GENDONG	2.665	3.547	
092	SEMBALUN	005	SEMBALUN	PANAN WISATA PUSUK	4.450	2.000	
093	LENER	010	LENER DUREN	SUMI PERKENMAHAN TANGKOK ADENG	277	245	
JUMLAH					179.257	234.233	

Based on the recapitulation data of the number of tourist visits in tourist destinations in East Lombok Regency as of 31 December 2023, we can see a significant growth in the number of visitors, which has implications for the number of tourists. tourism potential in the region. With total visitors increasing from 179,257 in 2022 to 234,233 in 2023.

Lombok Timur shows great potential in supporting the development of the tourism industry sector, especially in the hotel and *resort* industry.

Figure 6. Number of Star and Non-Star Hotels In Lombok Timur

Klasifikasi Hotel	Banyaknya Hotel Bintang dan Non Bintang (Unit)	
	2022	2023
Hotel Bintang	1	1
Hotel Non Bintang	135	133
Jumlah	136	134

Based on the data in the figure above, if we look at the stability of this star hotel, although the number of star hotels remains the same, which is only 1 unit, this shows that the star hotel accommodation sector has not developed significantly in East Lombok. In fact, star hotels usually attract tourists with higher purchasing power and provide more complete facilities. This could be an indication that the potential for luxury accommodation has not been optimally utilised or there are usually several obstacles in the construction of star hotels in the East Lombok area.

The decline in the number of non- star hotels from 135 units to 133 units indicates that there is a decline in accommodation capacity in this sector. This decline could be due to various factors, such as changes in traveller demand, hotel closures due to inability to compete, or financial challenges due to the pandemic affecting the ability of small hotels to survive.

Figure 7. Population, Population Density, and Sex Ration by Sub-district in Lombok Timur District in 2024

Kecamatan	Jumlah Penduduk	Laju Pertumbuhan Penduduk per Tahun	Persentase Penduduk	Kepadatan Penduduk per km persegi (km2)	Rasio Jenis Kelamin Penduduk
Keruwak	61067	0,99	4,35	1508	98,6
Jerowaru	66171	1,04	4,71	463	99,5
Sakra	68051	0,84	4,85	2712	98,2
Sakra Barat	61465	0,9	4,38	1003	100,1
Sakra Timur	55346	0,79	3,94	1494	100,6
Terara	80780	0,66	5,75	1951	101,2
Montong Gading	50910	0,94	3,63	1984	99,5
Sikur	83048	1,14	5,91	1061	101,2
Masbagik	113439	0,89	8,08	3420	99,7
Pringasele	67250	1,03	4,79	501	100,4
Sukarnuli	38420	0,76	2,74	2651	97,1
Suralaga	67793	0,46	4,83	2509	97,5
Selong	96015	0,55	6,84	3031	98,8
Labuhan Haji	67448	0,72	4,8	1361	97,9
Pringgabaya	117161	1	8,34	860	98,1
Sulela	48513	0,83	3,45	422	98,6
Alkmei	74219	0,97	5,28	915	98,2
Wanasaba	74466	1,07	5,3	1332	98,2
Sembalun	25190	1,1	1,79	116	102,3
Lenek	47444	1,4	3,38	1134	97,5
Sambelia	40147	0,47	2,86	164	101,1
Lombok Timur	1404343	0,88	100	875	99,2

Lombok Timur’s population growth of 0.88% with growth in the accommodation and food and beverage sector of 10.07% shows a positive trend, especially when compared to the national average. Growth in the tourism and accommodation sector is very promising, indicating an increase in demand and economic activity in this area.

The East Lombok District Government is also quite proactive in encouraging infrastructure development, especially in strategic areas such as Sembalun and Jerowaru which have natural tourist attractions. Road repairs, construction of public facilities, and promotion of ecotourism have strengthened East Lombok’s position as a leading tourism destination.

With these efforts, East Lombok is increasingly becoming an attractive area for investors, especially in the accommodation and tourism sectors. The development of star hotels, eco-resorts, as well as cultural and community-based lodging offers great business opportunities along with the increasing interest of tourists both local and foreign.

Based on demographic data and regional analysis in East Lombok, the potential of the accommodation industry has good prospects, especially with the increasing contribution of the accommodation and food and beverage provision sector in GRDP. Sub-districts with high population densities such as Selong, Sakra, and Masbagik is suitable for large-scale hotel development.

2.6. Linkage of Hotel and Resort Accommodation Industry in East Lombok to MSME Empowerment

MSMEs are one of the business sectors in national economic growth that must be empowered and developed. The presence of MSMEs has been regulated in laws and regulations but has not adapted to the development of disruption in the digital economy. The adaptation needed by MSMEs is the use of information technology as a medium in developing their business. (Saputri, 2023)

The West Nusa Tenggara Provincial Government encourages MSME players and the hotel and restaurant industry in the West Nusa Tenggara region to establish cooperation and partnerships in marketing their superior products. According to an ANTARA article, West Nusa Tenggara Deputy Governor Sitti Rohmi Djalilah said that MSME products must also pay attention to the quality and quantity of their products. Both in terms of the availability of raw materials, intensity and sustainability of products and product packaging.

West Nusa Tenggara has abundant potential which is good to be developed and utilised by MSMEs. In the hospitality industry, of course, local MSMEs need materials and products to complement hotel needs such as soap, shampoo, coffee, tea and basic food ingredients for daily consumption of hotel visitors.

The link between the hotel and resort accommodation industry can be done in a way where the hotel provides sales of souvenirs typical of Lombok, West Nusa Tenggara in hotels and resorts so that hotel visitors can buy these souvenirs, which can support the welfare of MSMEs in the hotel and resort sector.

MSMEs in East Lombok must be involved for the sustainability and success of a hospitality industry. By involving MSMEs, hotels and resorts help drive local economic growth. MSMEs create jobs, empower communities and help reduce economic inequality in the region. This in turn creates social stability that supports the hospitality industry as a whole.

By supporting MSMEs, the hospitality industry also helps develop skills and employment opportunities for local communities. This not only improves social welfare but also strengthens the overall economic foundation of the region.

3. Conclusion

As an area rich in natural and cultural tourism potential, East Lombok Regency has great opportunities in the development of the hotel and resort accommodation industry. One of the strategic steps that can be taken is the development of ecotourism *resorts* and hotels based on local culture, which can become a tourist icon of East Lombok.

By combining local wisdom and environmentally friendly concepts, East Lombok can attract investors to build accommodation that is unique and regional, but still modern and in line with the needs of international travellers.

With multifunctional facilities, hotels and resorts in East Lombok can also be used for national meetings, international conferences, and arts events, making this area a centre of economic activity, tourism, and culture that is attractive to investors and tourists. Based on this analysis, East Lombok's readiness for the hotel and resort accommodation industry is promising. With rich tourism potential, positive economic growth, evolving infrastructure, and support from the government and community, East Lombok is on track to become a leading tourism destination in Indonesia.

4. Suggestions

As described in this article, East Lombok has enormous potential in the Hospitality and Resort Industry which is certainly supported by the potential of Tourism in Lombok, West Nusa Tenggara which can attract tourists. However, to carry out the planning and development of the Industry there are suggestions that must be considered to make the business of the hotel and resort industry in East Lombok sustainable and long-term. Among them are:

1. Investment in the construction of star hotels in East Lombok has great potential and success to attract tourists with high purchasing power. However, it is necessary to pay attention to obstacles such as local regulations and infrastructure, and diversification of tourism products must also be developed such as the existence of high-end and international standard supporting facilities because Lombok tourists are mostly foreign tourists which can strengthen the attractiveness of the development of the hotel and resort accommodation industry in East Lombok in particular.
2. Involve all local communities and other stakeholders in the planning and development of the hotel and resort accommodation industry in Lombok.
3. Strategic areas such as Sembalun and Jerowaru have the potential to develop a high-end hotel and resort accommodation industry. However, in these areas the infrastructure must be improved, which can be done in collaboration between the local government and investors so that an attractive hotel and resort accommodation industry will be created and attract tourists in East Lombok.
4. Investors can capitalise on opportunities by investing in the development of star hotels, eco-resorts, or culturally-based lodging that is increasingly in demand by local and international tourists in the East

Lombok region, which by looking at With the global trend towards ecotourism, investment in eco-lodges and community-based lodges will be very promising.

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